

ELECTROLBERT: Combining Replaced Token Detection and Sentence Order Prediction

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Abstract

ELECTROLBERT is a novel transformer algorithm that combines the replaced token prediction of the ELECTRA system [1] with the sentence order prediction used in the ALBERT system [2]. As reported, the default next sentence prediction component used in most BERT-based transformers has the drawback that a random next sentence can be easily predicted based on its different scope. The sentence order prediction facilitates the detection of semantic flow and is well suited for finetuning question answering systems, as the pairing of a question with text related to the correct answer resembles the correct order of two sentences in a scientific text. The implementation of ELECTROLBERT is based on the BioELECTRA [3] code. ELECTROLBERT is pretrained on the 2022 baseline set of all PubMed abstracts provided by the National Library of Medicine and two predictors are finetuned using pairs of relevant and non-relevant question-abstract pairs for document prediction and examples for the "yes/no" type questions, both generated using the BioASQ10 training dataset [4]. For each novel question in the document prediction task of BioASQ10, 6750 Pubmed abstracts are filtered for processing by ELECTROLBERT from all Pubmed abstracts using a combination of the GENSIM topic modelling system [5] and a simple infrequent word detection method. The system was continuously improved during the BioASQ10 competition and in the last batch, ELECTROLBERT ranked as the 3rd team for document prediction and 1st place and team for the "yes/no" type questions.